
USING XGBOOST MODEL WITH FEATURE SELECTION TECHNIQUES FOR WIND SPEED FORECASTING *

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ABSTRACT

In the past various machine learning models have been employed for Wind Speed forecasting relating to the optimal design of turbines or for system planning. But proper tools are essentially needed for forecasting with the highest accuracy. In this groundwork, extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) model with the feature selection techniques include the feature importance and principle component analysis (PCA) are employed for short-term Wind Speed forecasting. The model is trained on the data sets of the city Bahawalpur and it showed that the feature importance technique outperforms the PCA method.

Keywords machine learning · forecasting · XGBoost

1 Introduction

Renewable Energy Sources have a lot of importance in today's world for the production of electrical output. The main reasons that every government and policymaker in this world nowadays prefers Renewable Energy in the wake of global warming and limited availability of fossil fuels [1]. The Renewable Energy Sources are hazard-less, population free, eco-friendly, freely available in nature in vast quantities and most importantly they give a chance to create a carbon-free environment.

Wind Energy is the most eminent source for a renewable energy source, it is a significant way for the production of electricity with the increased demand for electricity generation and has the potential to achieve sustainable energy supply and constitutes a keystone component for micro-grids in a way towards the smart grid infrastructure[2]. The majority of the world's electricity requirement, not only for domestic purposes but also for services and trades at large scale can be realistically provided by the wind energy by the middle of the energy. However, stochastic and intermittent wind power generation poses several challenges to the large scale penetration of wind power. These wind-related uncertainties can put the system reliability and power quality at risk with the increasing penetration of wind power and thus, the main grid integration issues such as balanced management and reserve capacities can come into question. Reducing the need for balancing energy and making the power generation scheduling and dispatch decisions can be realized with the help of wind speed and power generation forecasts. The forecasting of Wind speed has a direct effect on the power forecasting as the speed of the wind is directly proportional to the cube root of wind power[3]. Wind power forecasting plays a key role in developing and planning the Wind Power Operating System. Furthermore, the forecasts can play a vital role in keeping the costs competitive by reducing the need for wind curtailments and thereby, increasing revenue in electricity market operations. However, the random and unstable characteristics of the wind make it considerably difficult to forecast the wind speed and power accurately. Hence, extensive efforts have been devoted to the developments and improvements of wind speed and power forecasting approaches by numerous energy and

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environment-related research centers and universities. The better and more accurately predicted wind power decreases the chances of the worsened outcome in wind power operating systems. [2, 4]

From the last decade, machine learning has made significant improvements and showed fruitful results in different fields from classification tasks to automation. In the past various machine learning methods have been implemented for wind speed forecasting such as the works mentioned in [5, 6]. The objective of this work is to employ the new XGBoost model [7] with two feature selection methods for short term Wind Speed forecasting. The XGBoost model is relatively new machine learning and has gained significant importance due to the high accuracy output and fast processing time while being complex [7].

Figure 1: Temperature, pressure and humidity by hours and monthly means.

2 Methodology

In this analysis, XGBoost is used as machine learning to train the model with two feature selections methods, the PCA and the feature importance. Afterward, the trained model is used on the test data sets for both cases to find out which features selection technique performs best.

2.1 Data

The data that have been used in this literature is taken from energydata.info via world bank [8] which consists of a repository for measurements from 12 wind masts in Pakistan. In this literature, only the data of one city, Bahawalpur, have been utilized. The data consists of various weather parameters within a 10 minutes interval from April 2016 to August 2018. In this analysis, only the last 90 days of data have been selected which comprises of 17712 measurements with 7 features after pre-processing. The features are Wind Speed (m/s), wind direction, humidity, temperature (centigrade), pressure (hPa), day of the year, time of the day and length of a day. The Length of Day has been obtained by utilizing sunrise time and sunset time, that are obtained from NOAA Solar Calculator[9] for each day and the subtraction of sunset time from sunrise time leads to the length of a day.

Figure 1 illustrate the plot of the temperature, pressure, and humidity. The color bars represent the magnitude of the measures, bright color infers lower magnitude and darker color tell us higher magnitude. The first column in Figure 1 gives us the information about the hourly average values and the second column provides the visualization for the monthly average values. The first row represents the wind speed, the attribute is to be forecast in the literature. The information from these subplots allow us to identify the correlation among the attributes of data set.

2.2 XGBoost

XGBoost is the machine learning algorithm based upon Gradient Boosted decision trees (GBDT) [10]. The XGBoost performs better than other machine learning models due to the introduction of Taylor expansion for the cost function by incorporating the second derivative to provide the results with more accuracy and its avoid voiding overfitting by using shrinkage and regularisation techniques [7].

A Decision tree (DT) has the similar characteristics with the real tree as shown in figure 2. The DT algorithms begin from the root node and then moves towards internal nodes corresponds to an attribute and finally lead to leaf nodes that correspond to a class label. The GDBT is an ensemble learning method that utilizes a chain of decision trees , from which the DT gathers knowledge from previous DT and influence the next tree to refine the model and built a strong learner [11].

Figure 2: The observed and predicted data using XGBoost with features from PCA

In XGBoost model several parameters can be tuned to get the best-performing model. Parameter tuning is an essential step to prevent over-fitting in the model, which is caused when the model tries to label the random fluctuations or noises as value able facts. The three parameters (maximum depth of trees, the step size, and the number of trees) are selected in our model. The parameters that have been employed in our model are.

- n_trees: represents the number of trees that are employed in the model.
- eta: analogous to the learning rate, defines how quickly the model learns
- max_depth: relates to the maximum number of splits, the more increase in the maximum depth can cause the over-fitting in the model.
- subsample:it is used to reduce the variance of the model and prevent over-fitting.

2.3 Feature Selection

In this research, two approaches have been implemented for the feature selection; the feature importance and PCA.

The PCA is a procedure for reducing the dimensionality of the variable space by representing it with a few orthogonal (uncorrelated) variables that capture most of its variability[12]. In this literature, the PCA is utilized for the moderate dimensional features to get rid of irrelevant feature noises and hence providing improvement in forecasting accuracy. By incorporating the PCA method the seven features have been reduced to 3 components. Table 1 list the first sample obtained from PCA.

Feature importance is one of the random forest tree approaches. This method uses a backpropagation procedure to repetitively eliminate features that are too small to consider, based upon r^2 score [13].

Component 1	Component 2	Component 3
-428.999663	12.418122	-1.049804

Table 1: Samples of principal components with PCA technique

Table 2 lists the r^2 scores at each iteration by utilizing the feature importance method with the constraint of having minimum of three features. The r^2 scores increases as the number of features decrease with the last iterative having the highest value of r^2 . Therefore features from iterative 3 are selected with the features selection method.

Itt	Features	r^2 Score
0	Temperature, Pressure, WindDirection(Degrees), DayLength(s), DayOfYear, TimeOfDay(s)	0.865
1	Temperature, Pressure, WindDirection(Degrees), DayOfYear, TimeOfDay(s)	0.857
2	Pressure, WindDirection(Degrees), DayOfYear, TimeOfDay(s)	0.853
3	Pressure, DayOfYear, TimeOfDay(s)	0.884

Table 2: The r^2 score at each iteration using the feature importance method

2.4 Setup

The data with the selected features from the last section were split into two categories: the 80% of the data divided as the training set and while the remaining 20% of data are divided into the testing set. The root mean square error (RMSE) and r^2 score are used to calculate the accuracy, and efficiency respectively.

The chosen values for the parameters for both techniques, feature importance, and PCA, in XGBoost are as follows; maximum depth of trees: 13, the step size: 0.05 , the subsample': 0.7 and the number of trees: 70.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 3: The observed and predicted data using XGBoost with features from feature importance

Two cases have been considered to justify the feature selection techniques works best for wind speed forecasting with XGBoost model. Table 3 list the root mean square errors and the r^2 scores for each scenario.

From the table 3 it can be seen that feature importance method has the best performance with the least RMSE (0.64) and the highest r^2 value (0.89) , while PCA also showed the promising results but reasons it didn't excel is due to following statements.

Figure 4: The observed and predicted data using XGBoost with features from PCA

- In PCA the values from all of the original variables are transformed into the lower-dimensional space.
- Only linear relationships are taken into account in the PCA method.
- PCA does not consider the potential multivariate nature of the data structure.

Figure 3 and 4 visualizes the observed and predicted wind speed using the XGBoost model with features from the feature importance and PCA methods respectively.

	RMSE	r^2 Score
Feature Importance	0.64	0.89
PCA	0.79	0.83

Table 3: Root mean square errors and the r^2 scores for both feature selection technique

The weather forecasting model can help policymakers to locate the best position for the setup wind turbine and the optimal designing of the instrumentation that would be beneficial for the inhabitants of these cities. It also helps in providing the groundwork for the solar panels as well and the temperature modeling of these cities.

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